

LOCAL FRACTURE MECHANICS ANALYSIS OF STRINGER PULL-OFF AND DELAMINATION IN A POST-BUCKLED COMPRESSION PANEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes some of the current global/local testing and analysis approaches to evaluating the design of composite structure. A case study for the local, fracture mechanics analysis of failure in a 4-stringer compression panel is described in detail. The analysis investigates the variation of strain energy release rate, G , with debond length using a 2-D plane strain finite element analysis (FEA) of one of the stringers. The boundary conditions on the local model were determined from a global shell element model of the panel. The values of G for these two damage modes were compared with the material's fracture toughness.

INTRODUCTION

Integrally stiffened, thin skin composite construction is used extensively in aircraft structure such as fuselage, nacelles, and lifting surfaces. Integrally stiffened panels consist of longitudinal or transverse members, or both. These members may be stiffeners, stringers, or frames and are co-cured or co-bonded or, to a lesser extent, secondary bonded to the skin, and may have various cross-sectional configurations. The stiffened panel represents one design method for high stiffness, light weight structure and is based on conventional metallic designs. The high stiffness, low weight

Figure 1 Building Block Approach

requirement is particularly pertinent to the aerospace industry. It will also become of more interest to other industries requiring the same performance requirements from composite materials, e.g. automobile bodies, boat hulls, etc. The loading on these panels is dependent on where in the structure they will be used. In an aircraft wing-box, the more dominant loading will be compression [1] or shear through torsion of the wing-box [2], in the crown panel of a composite fuselage the predominant load may be tension or compression with pressurisation [3].

The design of such structure usually requires a "building block" approach to testing. This approach involves increasing the testing complexity and size from coupon tests to full scale structural tests, Fig. 1. The tests involved in the building block approach, particularly the larger structural tests, are expensive in terms of specimen production and test set-up. The results from these tests only help to provide qualitative verification data still requiring analysis to scale-up to the final structure. To decrease these costs, advantage should be taken of analytical methods to predict failure and verify design. The multi-stringer panel is generally designed to operate at loads several times the initial buckling load. With efficient non-linear finite element analyses, the initial buckling and post-buckling deformations of these panels may be predicted [4]. However, the analytical methods to predict failure of the panel are less efficient, and hence, panels are invariably tested to evaluate design and determine failure load. The initiation of final failure of the panel after buckling is usually identified as separation of the stiffener by debonding or delamination.

What is required to reduce cost and increase efficiency of structural design and structural failure prediction is a global/local testing and analysis approach that provides further, less expensive steps to the building block approach. The global/local approach involves supporting the global tests and analyses used in the traditional design approaches, described above, by innovative local sub-element tests. These sub-element tests focus in on the critical areas of the structure and the local analyses incorporate fracture mechanics for damage prediction in these critical areas. The local analyses also may act as the analysis of the local sub-element test. These sub-element tests are intended to be in between a coupon and a sub-structure test. They are cheaper to manufacture and test, allowing parametric studies to be conducted. They also fully represent of structures undergoing the same manufacturing processes, and may even be cut from an actual structure.

Examples of the innovative global/local tests include the three and four point bending tests to simulate the loads on the stringer flange/skin interface from pressurisation of a fuselage structure [5], or the moments applied to a stringer from post-buckling of a compression panel [6]. When testing these local tests, it is imperative to impose all the significant loads and moments in all directions that are present in the structure and derived from the global analysis. Often, the design of these tests is limited by the use of a conventional load frame with one direction of loading and innovative fixturing is required. The design of these tests can be aided by the incorporation of a second loading direction by using a multi-axial load frame. The use of the second or even third loading direction reduces the need for innovative fixturing.

This paper describes some of the current global/local testing approaches and describes a local analysis of a 4-stringer compression panel and how fracture mechanics may be incorporated into the local analysis to predict failure of the panel.

THE GLOBAL/LOCAL DESIGN APPROACH

The global/local design approach incorporates both global/local analyses and testing. The traditional methods of design are used to generate an overall design of the structure. A global, 2D shell, finite element analysis may be used to determine the stress distribution. This stress distribution will help to identify critical areas of the structure where damage and eventually failure might initiate. However, in-plane failure theories using the stresses from this global model

generally fail to identify those areas, such as structural or material discontinuities, where failure will initiate from interlaminar stresses. With the use of 3D, local models of these critical areas more information on intralaminar and interlaminar failure may be determined. These local models may be either secondary sub-models of the structure with the appropriate boundary conditions from the global model imposed [7] or local 3-D models incorporated into the global model by the use of transition elements [8]. These models may be used to design the local sub-element tests that, in turn, may be used to redesign the global structure to minimise areas where transverse or interlaminar stresses are high. By incorporating fracture mechanics into the analysis of these sub-element tests, durability and damage tolerance may be predicted. Lastly, by looking at the accumulation of damage the fail safety of the structure can be determined.

Figure 2 2D Plane Strain Model of Skin and Stringer

CASE STUDY - 4 STRINGER, COMPRESSION PANEL

This section of the paper describes the fracture mechanics approach to predict stringer debond analyses of a 4-stringer compression panel made possible by local analysis. The panel was tested and analysed globally at NASA Langley [4] and consisted of a sixteen ply skin, a tapered flange, an eleven ply stiffener web, and a fifty ply cap. The composite parts of the panel were fabricated of carbon/brittle epoxy, T300/5208, and the stiffeners were secondary bonded to the skin 140mm apart using American Cyanamid FM-73. The panel buckled at 205kN and failed at 518kN (equivalent to $1300\mu\epsilon$ and $3500\mu\epsilon$, respectively). Failure occurred when the skin and inner stiffeners separated from one another. A post test inspection of the panel showed both an adhesive failure and delamination in the skin under the end of the flange. A delamination in the 50 ply cap was also observed. The global finite element model of the panel used in Ref. 4 was solved using STAGS, a non-linear, general finite element code. This code was used to predict the post-buckling response of the panel. Buckling loads were compared with PASCO a buckling analysis computer code. The predicted buckling load was 243 kN and no attempt was made to predict failure.

The local finite element models were determined from the identification of damage in the post test inspection. These models are of the stringer debond and the edge delamination in the cap. In design, local models such as these would be made of all likely damage initiation areas and stress/strain based or fracture criteria used to identify which area is more likely to fail first.

LOCAL STRINGER DEBOND MODEL

To characterise the debond of the stringers, a local, 2-D, plane strain finite element model was created of a section of one of the stringers and the skin, Fig. 2. The model was solved using MSC NASTRAN, and consisted primarily of NASTRAN's CQUAD4 elements with CTRIA3 elements used in certain locations to facilitate mesh transition. At one end of the flange on a stringer, a debond was modelled by using coincident nodes. Because of the thinness of the adhesive layer, the adhesive was not explicitly modelled. The debond was modelled as separation between the outer plies of the flange and skin. To allow different delamination lengths to be modelled, the coincident nodes on the upper and lower surfaces were constrained together or released using multi-point constraints. At the edge of the flange, elements were square and were one quarter of a ply thickness in size. Further away from the end of the flange, closer to the web, and throughout the flange the element size increased to one ply thickness square. In the regions away from the debond such as the cap, and the left hand side of the model, larger elements covering several plies were used. The properties for these elements were smeared and were calculated using classical laminated plate theory. The noodle region between the curved transition from the web to the flange was modelled as an isotropic material with a modulus equivalent to E_{22} . The model had 1939 elements and 2126 nodes.

Table 1 Displacements and Forces derived from Global Model

End	δ_y (mm)	δ_z (mm)	N_y (N/mm)	Q_y (N)	M_y (mm-N)
A	-0.0164	-3.279	-129	119	-772
B	0.0212	1.988	-222	107	-960

Vertical and horizontal displacements were applied to either end of the skin and the cap was fixed. These displacements were obtained from the global shell element model [4] and represented the displacements of the skin at the maximum buckled location with the experimental failure load applied to the global model. The displacements, forces and moments are given in Table 1. Strain energy release rate, G , and the individual modes, G_I and G_{II} , were calculated using the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) and also using Eqn [1]

$$G = \frac{U_{i+1} - U_i}{a_{i+1} - a_i} \tag{1}$$

where U_i is the total energy and a_i is the debond length at debond increment i .

EDGE DELAMINATION OF CAP

Edge delamination of the cap was modelled using a closed form solution for G for edge delamination [9] in the cap with a compressive strain of $3500\mu\epsilon$ applied. The web, flange and skin were not included in the model. For edge delamination, G increases from zero (or near zero) at zero delamination length and quickly reaches a plateau value where it ceases to change with an increase in delamination length. It is the value of G at the plateau that is used to predict edge delamination. The closed form solution for edge delamination generally gives the values of G at the plateau for thinner laminates. To confirm that the closed form solution gave plateau values for thicker laminates, a quasi-3D finite element analysis, Q3DG [10] was also used. The Q3DG analysis was also used to give the individual modal values of G , G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} , using VCCT.

tapered laminate, the value of G at the peak in the G versus a curve was considered to be G_c and was used to predict delamination onset [12]. For delamination growth from a matrix crack in a curved laminate [13], where G increased continuously with a , the point of inflection in the G versus a curve was postulated to give the critical value of G required to predict delamination onset.

Figure 4 Critical Value of G for Delamination Initiation

longer satisfied. Calculating G_{total} from Eqn [1], shown by the solid line, shows this method compares very well with the VCCT method except at smaller delamination lengths. The curve using Eqn [1] does decrease at the free end presumably to zero. For this example, extrapolating the G_{total} versus a curve to zero or using the point of inflection as in Ref. 13, gives a similar critical value of G for initiation of the debond of 230 J/m^2 . From Ref. 9, the T300/5208 composite G_{Ic} is approximately 140 J/m^2 , G_{IIc} is approximately 900 J/m^2 , and using a linear fracture failure criterion G_c for a mode ratio of $G_I/G_{II} = 1.5$, the mixed mode toughness is approximately

Observation of the VCCT data in Fig. 4 close to zero crack length shows the G_{total} curve increases as the debond length reaches zero. This is probably an effect of element size compared to the delamination length. With VCCT, there is an assumption that the delamination length is much larger than the increment of crack growth. For small delamination lengths this condition is no

Figure 5 Variation of G with Delamination Length in the Cap

230 J/m^2 , the value of the strain energy release rate at the end of the flange. Data from Ref. 14 on using FM73 adhesive as a toughening interlayer gave a G_{Ic} of 975 J/m^2 , and a G_{IIc} of 1840 J/m^2 . The FM73 values are for an interleaf material and may not be relevant to the adhesive bondline.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

STRINGER DEBOND MODEL

The plot of G_{total} versus debond length for debond of the stringer is given in Fig. 3 along with its G_I and G_{II} components. This plot gives three pieces of information that will help predict component failure or allow redesign. First, the value of G_{total} comprises of approximately 60% G_I . In most polymeric adhesives and composite materials the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , is significantly less than the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IIc} . For brittle epoxies this difference can be as much as an order of magnitude. Hence, if the geometry of the part or the lay-up, or even the material can be altered to give a lower quantity of G_I , or to reduce the peel stresses, the panel will be more damage resistant and damage tolerant. The individual modes of G_{total} when calculated using the VCCT are dependent on mesh size if the crack is grown in a bimaterial interface. For a cohesive debond where the crack grows within the adhesive, the material is the same either side of the crack and there is no mesh size dependency. However, for a delamination where the ply angle above and below the delamination may be different a method to reduce the effect of mesh size must be adopted. One approach is the $\beta=0$ approach [11], where the bimaterial constant, ϵ , in the near tip stress field equation is forced to zero by forcing β to zero. This is achieved by adjusting the value of a non-dominant material property in the ply above the delamination.

Figure 3 G versus a Plot for a Post-buckled 4-stringer Panel

The second piece of information from Fig. 3 is the general relation between G_{total} and a . For crack lengths over 0.5mm the slope is positive, indicating that the crack growth will be unstable, or the crack will continue to grow with no increase in applied load. The slope of the curve under 0.5mm is positive, and this is discussed below. Once the stringer has begun to debond it will come completely off and the panel will fail. After approximately 10mm of crack growth, the slope of the G_{total} versus a curve becomes negative indicating stable growth. However, the value of G_{total} is still higher than that when the debond initiated. It is not until the point on the curve where the value of G_{total} becomes less than the value to initiate the crack, that the crack will cease to grow. The crack or delamination may grow a little beyond this point because of dynamic effects of the crack growth or short term creep while the crack is highly loaded, or both. For this example, the stringer would become separated before G decreased below the value at initiation. If the geometry of the stringer can be altered to reduce the slope of the G_{total} versus a curve such that it becomes negative either totally or over a large part of the stringer flange, then the structure would have a degree of damage tolerance.

The third piece of information from Fig. 3 is the value of G to initiate the delamination. Because there is a sudden termination at the end of the flange a stress singularity exists. Thus, if a stress analysis is used to determine the stresses at this point, the values of this stress will depend on the size of the elements used. However, it is possible to use the G versus a relationship to compare to the material's interlaminar fracture toughness. For edge delamination in a flat multidirectional laminate, G increases from zero to a plateau within a few ply thicknesses from the edge, as discussed above and the plateau value used to predict delamination onset at the edge [9]. In a

These values were used for comparison because no others were found in the literature. Hence, the panel would be more prone to delaminate between layers than debond in the adhesive layer. Therefore, at the failure strain, the fracture mechanics analysis predicts that the stringer will not only begin to debond but that debonding will continue and the panel should fail.

In this model the crack was modelled at the adhesive bondline, if the panel failed by delamination between plies in the skin, then this would need to be modelled. Also, the model assumed that the moments and forces, or the displacements imposed, did not alter as the debond grew. As the debond grows, the separation of the stringers, originally 140mm, effectively increases. As the distance increases the buckle in the skin can grow in size altering the loads and moments on the local model. To model this effect, either an integrated global/local model could be made or the global model re-run with either a debond modelled or a reduced size of flange and updated boundary conditions applied to the local model.

EDGE DELAMINATION OF THE CAP

The variation of G_{total} and its individual modes with debond length for edge delamination of the cap is shown in Fig. 5. The plot of G_{total} contains the closed form solutions and the Q3DG results. Generally, the comparison between the closed form solution and the plateau values of the Q3DG solution are good. Because of the thick nature of the cap, the plateau values are reached after several millimetres of crack growth, unlike thinner laminates where the plateau may be reached after only a few ply thicknesses, or less than 1mm. However, if the assumption remains that the plateau values of G_{total} is the critical value to initiate delamination, then using a total G failure criterion, the delamination is likely to occur between the 8th and 9th ply, or between the 45 and -45 degree ply where the interlaminar stresses were tensile. For this interface the value of G is approximately 110 J/m^2 , which is similar to the G_{IC} value for the composite, indicating that edge delamination, may occur as an initial failure mode. However, it is more probable that as the stringer is disbonded, more load is transferred to the cap. To model this, the changes in the load in the cap should be determined as the debond grows in a progressive damage scenario.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

To reduce the cost of design and evaluation of composite structure, a global/local testing and analysis approach must be developed to add supplemental information to the "Building Block" approach. This paper demonstrated examples of innovative local tests and local analysis of a typical aerospace structure. The local testing should include tests that investigate the effect of structural loads on the regions of the structure where damage is likely to initiate such as free edges, bondline, etc. The local analysis should include 2D and 3D models of the likely damage areas and incorporate fracture analysis to predict durability and damage tolerance of the critical part and, hence, the structure. In a case study of the local, fracture mechanics analysis of failure in a 4-stringer compression panel, the critical areas were considered to be the free edge of the cap and the bondline of the stringer at the location of the buckle. Fracture mechanics analyses was used with finite element analysis to determine critical values of strain energy release rate, G , for these two critical areas. With the experimental failure load applied to the global model of the panel, the values of G were similar to the material's interlaminar fracture toughness indicating delamination was the predominant failure mode.

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